

Digital Twin Irrigation Strategies to Mitigate Drought Effects in Processing Tomatoes

Sandra Millán^{1*}, Jaume Casadesús², Jose María Vadillo¹ and Carlos Campillo¹

¹ Centre for Scientific and Technological Research of Extremadura (CICYTEX), Agronomy of Horticultural Crops, Finca La Orden, Highway A-V, Km 372, Guadajira, 06187 Badajoz, Spain; josemaria.vadilloh@juntaex.es (J.M.V.); carlos.campillo@juntaex.es (C.C.)

² Program of Efficient Use of Water in Agriculture, Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA), Parc de Gardeny (PCiTAL), Fruitcentre, 25003 Lleida, Spain; jaume.casadesus@irta.cat (J.C.)

* Correspondence: sandra.millan@juntaex.es (S.M)

Abstract

The increasing frequency and intensity of droughts, a direct consequence of climate change, represent one of the main threats to agriculture, especially for crops with a high water demand such as the processing tomato. The objective of this study is to evaluate the potential of the IrriDesK digital twin (DT) as a tool for automated irrigation management and the implementation of regulated deficit irrigation (RDI) strategies tailored to the crop's water status and phenological stage. The trial was conducted in an experimental plot over two consecutive growing seasons (2023–2024), comparing three irrigation treatments: full irrigation based on lysimeter measurements (T1) and two RDI strategies programmed through IrriDesK (T2 and T3). The results showed water consumption reductions of 30–45% in treatments T2 and T3 compared to treatment T1, with applied volumes of 277–400 mm versus approximately 570 mm in treatment T1, thus remaining within the sustainability threshold (<5,000 m³ ha⁻¹). The monitoring of leaf water potential (Ψ_{leaf}) and the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) confirmed the DT's ability to dynamically adjust irrigation and maintain an adequate water status during critical crop phases. In terms of productivity, treatment T1 achieved the highest yields (≈ 135 t ha⁻¹), while RDI strategies reduced production to 90–108 t ha⁻¹, but improved fruit quality, with increases in total soluble solids content of up to 10–15 % (°Brix). These results demonstrate that IrriDesK is an effective tool for the optimization of water use while maintaining crop profitability and enhancing the resilience of processing tomatoes to drought scenarios.

Keywords: precision irrigation; apparent electrical conductivity; regulated deficit irrigation; water use efficiency; NDVI

1. Introduction

Climate change is one of the main challenges for the future of society, significantly affecting agricultural production and food security [1]. This phenomenon is closely linked to the increase in greenhouse gas emissions and, consequently, the rise in the global average temperature and alterations in climate patterns [2]. These climate changes will lead to a greater frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, such as heat waves, floods, and droughts [3]. Of these events, drought is one of the most complex phenomena to predict [4] and is cumulative in nature [5], meaning that it becomes increasingly severe over

time [6]. Drought is defined as a prolonged period in which precipitation falls substantially below historical average levels [2]. Increased climate variability can lead to more pronounced fluctuations in crop yields [7], with repercussions for both farmers [8] and global markets. The increased frequency and intensity of droughts, combined with unsustainable water management practices, pose a major threat to the availability of this resource.

The processing tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum L.*) is a crop of great economic importance in Spain. In 2023, the country ranked as the fifth-largest global producer, behind the United States, China, Italy, and Turkey [9]. In Spain, the main processing tomato-producing region is Extremadura, accounting for approximately 70% of the national output [10]. This crop has a high water demand, with water requirements typically exceeding 600 mm per growing cycle in this region [11]. Due to its high water consumption, in drought-prone areas such as Extremadura, processing tomatoes are among the first crops affected by irrigation restrictions. As Pérez et al. [12] highlight, the Extremadura Agrarian Law (Law 6/2015) stipulates that, in water emergency situations, woody crops have priority for irrigation over annual crops, as is the case with processing tomatoes. Persistent drought in the region led to successive restrictions on irrigated land for two consecutive years, with the area reduced from 23,000 hectares in 2022 to 17,000 hectares in 2021 [13], significantly affecting one of the region's main crops. Therefore, there is significant interest within the sector in establishing crop management techniques that optimize water use.

One of the management techniques that can be employed during drought periods is the strategy of RDI. This strategy involves imposing water deficits during the phenological stages that are least sensitive to water stress with the aim of reducing vegetative growth while minimally affecting fruit yield and quality [14]. RDI strategies have been widely studied in the scientific community and their effectiveness in saving water and improving quality in various crops has been demonstrated [15-20]. To implement these strategies effectively, it is essential to know the crop's water requirements precisely, adapted to local conditions. In the case of the processing tomato in Extremadura, Campillo, [21] adjusted water requirements by considering the region's specific climatic and soil factors. However, such adjustments can be supplemented by more complex systems, such as weighing lysimeters, which allow the crop's water balance to be determined with great accuracy.

Weighing lysimeters constitute the reference method for measuring evapotranspiration (ET_o) [22], crop water uptake, and percolation losses [23], providing essential experimental data for evaluating the efficiency of different irrigation strategies, such as RDI [24]. However, weighing lysimeters represent a costly, fixed infrastructure, generally accessible only in research settings [25]. In the case of the processing tomato, their use enables the identification of the phenological stages most sensitive to water deficit and the quantification of how different irrigation levels affect both vegetative growth and fruit quality—key information for the development and validation of digital twins (DTs) and smart irrigation systems.

In the processing tomato, water deficit generally leads to a decrease in photosynthesis, vegetative growth and crop yield [26] but can also induce positive effects on certain fruit quality parameters, such as increased antioxidant compounds and greater sugar accumulation [27,28]. As reported by Quadir et al. [29], the application of RDI during the initial fruit set phase induces earlier red color development and can improve soluble solids content at harvest without significantly reducing yield. In the case of processing tomatoes, this increase in the fruit's total soluble solids content is very important, as it constitutes the primary quality indicator used to estimate the crop's economic yield [30]. However, despite the extensive scientific and technical knowledge base on optimal irrigation practices for each crop type and its phenological stage, the effective implementation of

these strategies in the field continues to pose a challenge. One of the main limitations lies in the lack of appropriate tools and the need for specific knowledge to accurately quantify and manage crop water requirements [31]. This situation hinders the efficient distribution of water at the right place and time.

In this context, the development of DT technology constitutes a key element in promoting more rational and sustainable management of available water resources. DTs are virtual representations interconnected in real time with physical systems, enabling the continuous and remote simulation, monitoring, and optimization of agricultural processes [32]. This emerging technology is gaining relevance in the agricultural sector by enabling predictive analyses based on the simulation of environmental conditions and the physiological response of crops [33]. Its potential also lies in the ability to integrate multiple information sources (such as satellite imagery, field sensor measurements, and historical climate variable records) to generate dynamic, high-precision models. In recent years, DTs have played an increasingly important role in irrigated agriculture, especially in optimizing water use through the implementation of smart farming practices [31]. Recent studies have employed DTs to integrate soil, climate, and crop sensors, with the aim of simulating irrigation strategies and optimizing water use [34,35]. Although studies on the use of DTs in processing tomato production remain scarce, recent experiments have demonstrated the potential of combining artificial intelligence (AI), sensors, and Internet of Things (IoT) platforms to optimize irrigation scheduling. Martelli et al. [36] developed a decision support system (DSS) for drip irrigation based on machine learning techniques for processing tomatoes. The DSS enabled the implementation of RDI strategies, resulting in significant water savings and improved fruit quality. Similarly, Galaverni et al. [37] developed an IoT platform for processing tomatoes that optimized irrigation, achieving water savings of up to 40% and paving the way for future advances through AI and DTs. More recently, Millán et al. [31] used a DT that enabled the application of RDI strategies in a commercial processing tomato plot with high spatial variability. This DT achieved greater water use efficiency, using less water and improving agronomic outcomes compared to the other plots managed with conventional practices and remote-sensing-based systems.

In this context, the validation of tools such as DTs under real-world growing conditions is crucial to advancing towards a more efficient, sustainable agriculture adapted to the challenges of precision irrigation in processing tomatoes. The objective of this study is to validate a DT under field conditions for the implementation of an automated drip irrigation system capable of applying RDI strategies tailored to the crop's water status and its different phenological phases. Additionally, an evaluation is made of whether this DT can achieve profitable yields with a water consumption limit of less than 5,000 m³/ha. The application of this digital technology to irrigation management aims to reduce water consumption under drought conditions without compromising yield or fruit quality (^oBrix), by implementing RDI strategies dynamically adjusted to crop needs.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of the study plot

The study was carried out over two growing seasons (2023–2024) on an experimental plot at “Finca La Orden” in Badajoz, Spain (latitude 38°51'19.06" N, longitude 6°40'18.90" W, datum WGS84), run by the Scientific and Technological Research Centre of Extremadura (Regional Government of Extremadura) (Figure 1a). The plot has an area of 6,000 m² cultivated with processing tomatoes (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.), variety H1015, established in a west–east orientation. Transplanting was carried out on 12 April 2023 and 10

April 2024. The crop was established with a planting pattern of 1.5 m × 0.24 m, corresponding to an approximate density of 27,777 plants ha⁻¹. The soil is classified texturally as loamy clay to sandy loam, with an average clay, silt and sand content of 27.59%, 28.34% and 46.39%, respectively. It has a slightly acidic pH, low organic matter content (0.62%), high bulk density (1.41 g/cm³), low cation exchange capacity (9.41 meq/100 g) and moderate to weak structure. Soil depth is greater than 2.5 m, with low stone content and the terrain is flat with a slope of 0%. The effective rooting depth is around 1 m. The climate of the study area is Mediterranean with a slight Atlantic influence. The rainfall regime is highly seasonal, with a dry season from June to September (summer) and a wet season from October to May (winter), during which approximately 80% of the annual precipitation is concentrated. For the period 2010–2024, the average ETo was 1303.56 mm, while the average annual precipitation was 473.65 mm. During the same period, the average maximum and minimum air temperatures were 23.89 °C and 9.80 °C, respectively. The warmest months are July and August, when maximum temperatures exceed 40 °C almost every year, although they rarely exceed 45 °C. In contrast, the coldest months are December and January, with minimum temperatures usually falling below 0 °C and reaching extreme values close to -5 °C in exceptional cases. The plot was divided into three sectors according to the irrigation management applied (T1, T2 and T3) with areas of 3,000 m², 1,500 m² and 1,500 m², respectively (Figure 1b). Fertilization as well as control of pests or diseases were those commonly used in commercial processing tomato techniques.

2.2. . Study of the spatial variability of the plot, selection of control points and soil texture analysis

Before transplanting the crop, on 14 October 2022, the Veris 3150 sensor (Veris Technologies Inc., Salina, KS, USA) was used to characterize the spatial variability of the plot by measuring the apparent electrical conductivity (ECa) of the soil. As the tractor pulls the Veris 3150 cart across the field, a pair of plough electrodes (rotating discs) injects current into the soil, while the remaining electrodes measure the voltage drop using a Wenner array configuration. The system is configured to alternate between two measurement modes: A (superficial) and B (deep). Configuration A uses the four inner discs (2, 3, 4, and 5), measuring the voltage between discs 3 and 4, while configuration B uses the four outer discs (1, 2, 5, and 6), measuring the voltage between discs 2 and 5. Thus, the Veris 3100 generates two sets of data: weighted surface measurements from 0 to 0.30 m and deep measurements from 0 to 0.90 m. This study analyzed measurements corresponding to the surface layer (0–0.30 m), given that most of the root activity of processing tomatoes is concentrated in the first 0.30 m of the soil profile. ECa measurements were taken along parallel transects approximately 3 m apart, and the final database contained 885 ECa values. A Beeline/RT20 system (NovAtel Inc., Calgary, Alberta, Canada) with sub-metric accuracy was used to georeference the measurements. In this way, latitude, longitude, and ECa data were recorded every second in the Veris data logger in ASCII format. Subsequently, this raw ASCII file was exported to QGIS 3.34.11 (QGIS Development Team, 2024; <https://www.qgis.org>), where the ECa values were interpolated using ordinary kriging. This enabled the map to be generated and homogeneous areas to be established in which the different irrigation treatments were applied. Three different zones were identified on the ECa map (Figure 1b): (I) green, corresponding to lighter soils, with low ECa values (<4.22 mS/m), a higher proportion of sand and lower water holding capacity; (II) yellow, characterized by intermediate ECa values (4.22–7.16 mS/m), with moderate texture and water holding capacity; and (III) white, which had the highest ECa values (>7.16 mS/m), associated with a more clayey texture and, therefore, greater water holding capacity. The differences observed in ECa values are due to the complex interaction of biological, agro-

nomie, edaphic, anthropogenic, topographic and climatic factors [38]. For irrigation programming, three control points (CPs) were selected in treatments T2 and T3, while in T1 six CPs were established to monitor the crop (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. (a) Location of the trial plot at CICYTEX (Badajoz, Spain), (b) Map showing the different irrigation treatments in the processing tomato plot (T1, T2 and T3), the different control points (numbered 1 to 12), and the different soil apparent electrical conductivity (Eca) zones as measured with a Veris 3150 sensor.

Table 1 shows the soil properties in the study area. On 25 March 2023, a soil sample was taken at each CP at a depth of 0.30 m. Subsequently, all samples were transferred to the laboratory in plastic bags, where they were left to air dry, ground and passed through a 2 mm sieve. Soil characterization focused on determining texture. Texture was evaluated using the hydrometer method [39].

Table 1. Texture analysis at each control point (CP).

Control Point	Clay (%)	Silt (%)	Sand (%)	USDA Texture
1	28.30	28.36	43.34	Clay loam
2	30.23	26.36	43.41	Clay loam
3	26.24	30.37	43.40	Loam
4	28.22	34.34	37.45	Clay loam
5	30.20	31.54	38.26	Clay loam
6	26.23	29.49	44.28	Clay
7	26.27	26.26	47.47	Sandy clay loam
8	26.29	32.27	41.44	Loam
9	26.30	26.36	47.34	Sandy clay loam
10	28.22	24.28	47.50	Sandy clay loam
11	26.28	24.20	49.52	Sandy clay loam
12	28.37	26.35	45.27	Sandy clay loam

2.3. Irrigation system and irrigation treatments

The processing tomatoes were irrigated daily using a drip irrigation system with 2.05 L/h emitters spaced 0.30 m apart. The experimental plot was subdivided into three elementary plots (irrigation sectors), in which three different irrigation treatments were applied: T1, T2, and T3.

The irrigation schedule applied in the treatments was as follows:

- T1: Irrigation was scheduled to meet crop water requirements throughout the growing cycle. The applied water was determined on a daily basis, using as a reference the crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) of the previous day, which was estimated with a weighing lysimeter (2.67 m × 2.25 m × 1.5 m). The lysimeter reproduced the same growing conditions as the rest of the experimental plot and was planted with two rows of processing tomato, each consisting of eight plants (Figure 2). The characteristics of the weighing lysimeter have been previously described by Picón-Toro et al. [40]. ET_c was determined based on the change in lysimeter weight between two consecutive measurements. The ET_o was obtained from an agrometeorological station located 100 m from the experimental plot, managed by the Extremadura Irrigation Advisory Network (<https://redarexplus.juntaex.es/RedarexPlus/>). The data were consulted daily from the start to the end of the irrigation campaign, applying the FAO-56 Penman-Monteith method [24], adjusted following Campillo et al. [21].

Figure 2. Surface view of the weighing lysimeter used in the study.

- T2: Irrigation scheduling was carried out using a DT called IrriDesK. This tool scheduled irrigation to meet the crop's water needs during its most sensitive phenological phases (transplanting, vegetative growth, and fruit development). During the ripening phase, it implemented an RDI strategy by applying 75% of ET_c. In IrriDesK, irrigation doses were calculated daily using a soil water balance model, adjusted to data from moisture sensors installed in the plot [41] and supplemented with local meteorological information (reference evapotranspiration, ET_o, provided by the SiAR agroclimatic station).
- T3: Irrigation scheduling was also carried out using IrriDesK. In this case, RDI was induced in the initial growth phase and subsequently during the ripening stage, coinciding with the strategy applied in treatment T2.

2.4. Description of the IrriDesK digital twin

IrriDesK (www.irridesk01.com) is a DT that enables automated precision irrigation by integrating crop information, sensor data, weather records, and simulation models [42] to estimate daily irrigation requirements. IrriDesK is available in a free version for research purposes and in a commercial version distributed by an external company. In this study, the research version (v.2023) of the IrriDesK DT was used for irrigation scheduling.

Before starting the irrigation campaign, the IrriDesK DT needs to be configured by providing it with the following information:

1. Plot information: The IrriDesK DT is first supplied with crop and soil properties. The crop selected was the processing tomato, with a maximum root depth of 0.4 m and maximum vigor of 0.8 (scale 0–1), expressed in terms of ground cover or intercepted radiation. The soil of the plot was classified as sandy clay loam according to the USDA, with a slope of 0% and a depth of 1 m. Soil water content was $0.31 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ at field capacity and $0.15 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ at permanent wilting point. A drip irrigation system was used with emitters spaced 0.30 m apart, a nominal flow rate of 2.05 L h^{-1} per emitter and a wet bulb diameter of 0.45 m, with beds spaced 1.5 m apart.

2. Sensor information: IrriDesK is then given the list of sensors to be integrated into the automatic irrigation system. In treatments T2 and T3, a series of sensors were installed at the previously selected CPs to carry out automatic precision irrigation. To monitor the wetting bulb in the drip zone, three Teros 10 probes (Decagon Devices, Inc., Pullman, WA, USA) were installed at a depth of 0.20 m (Figure 3a) and 0.10 m horizontally from the dripper towards the bed. The factory calibration provided by the manufacturer, which is recommended for mineral soils, was used for the Teros 10 sensors. Additionally, an MTKD water meter (LabFerrer S.L., Cervera, Lleida, Spain) was installed in each irrigation treatment to measure the amount of water applied and record irrigation events. Soil moisture sensors and the water meter were connected to an AgroBee-L H₂O data logger (Progress, Barcelona, Spain), which transmitted the information to the Agrónic 2500 controller (Progress, Barcelona, Spain) via LoRa communication (Figure 3b). The data were recorded hourly and stored on the Agrónic Web cloud platform (<https://agronic-web.com/>). IrriDesK downloaded the data stored on the Agrónic Web platform every day at 3:00 a.m. Weather information was obtained through the API of the Agroclimatic Information System for Irrigation (SiAR), from a station (Campbell Scientific, Logan, UT, USA) located 100 m from the plot and managed by the Scientific and Technological Research Centre of Extremadura.

Figure 3. (a) Teros 10 probe installed at a depth of 0.20 m and (b) Installation of the AgroBee-L H₂O on a pole in the experimental field at a height of 2.5 m.

3. Seasonal schedule information: The seasonal plan is defined as the estimate of the amount of water (mm) that the crop requires throughout the entire irrigation season. In this case, for processing tomato cultivation, a seasonal irrigation plan of 500 mm was defined. Additionally, it is necessary to establish an operating range by setting an upper limit (maximum allowable cumulative irrigation) and a lower limit (minimum acceptable cumulative irrigation) for the irrigation campaign. In this study, these thresholds were set at 650 mm and 400 mm, respectively (Figure 4). When cumulative irrigation tends to approach either of these values, the system adjusts the irrigation doses so that the total irrigation remains within the established limits. A more comprehensive description of the IrriDesK seasonal plan can be found in Millán et al. [31].

Figure 4. Range of cumulative irrigation thresholds, expressed in mm. Max is the maximum accumulated irrigation allowed, and Min is the minimum acceptable cumulative irrigation.

2.5. Soil moisture probes installed in the weighing lysimeter

In the weighing lysimeter, soil water content was monitored with five Drill&Drop moisture sensors (Sentek Sensor Technologies, Stepney, Australia). Probes S1, S2, S4, and S5 recorded soil water content in the 0–0.5 m depth profile, while probe S3 measured down to 0.8 m, allowing for the evaluation of deeper layers. In terms of spatial arrangement, sensors S1 and S5 were installed directly under the dripper, while S2 and S4 were positioned 0.20 m from the dripper, towards the crop bed (Figure 5a). The S3 probe was placed 1.5 m from the dripper (Figure 5a), also towards the bed, to evaluate moisture in the area farthest from the irrigated zone. This setup allowed monitoring of both the vertical and horizontal distribution of water applied by localized irrigation. All sensors were connected to a CR1000 datalogger (Campbell Scientific, Logan, UT, USA), which automatically stored the data every 30 minutes (Figure 5b).

Figure 5. (a) Installation of Drill&Drop sensors in the field, and (b) Superficial view of the CR100 data logger. S1, S2, S3, S4, and S5 correspond to the different Drill&Drop sensors.

2.6. Plant measurements

2.6.1. Phenological characterization of the crop

The determination of the crop development phases (Table 2) was carried out through visual assessments twice a week (Mondays and Thursdays), between 09:00 and 12:00 h, following the phenological stages described by Campillo et al. [43]. In each experimental plot, ten representative plants were randomly selected, and the dominant phenological stage was identified. In cases of heterogeneity, the percentage of plants in each stage was recorded. The transition between phases was considered complete when at least 80% of the plants in the plot exhibited the corresponding phenological stage. In addition, weekly measurements of the soil covered by the crop canopy were performed using aerial imagery acquired with a DJI Phantom 4 drone (DJI, Shenzhen, China) equipped with an RGB camera. The images were processed to determine the percentage of ground cover and to monitor the spatial evolution of crop development throughout the growing season. All treatments exhibited a similar phenological pattern, with no differences attributable to the experimental conditions applied.

Table 2. Crop phenology for the different study years.

Phenology	2023	2024
Phase I: Transplanting	12 April 2023	10 April 2024
Phase II: Rapid vegetative growth	21 April 2023	19 April 2024
Phase III: Fruit development	05 June 2023	03 June 2024

Phase IV: Ripening

03 July 2023

01 July 2024

2.6.2. Plant water status

The leaf water potential (Ψ_{leaf}) was measured weekly at each control point using a portable Pump-up pressure chamber (PMS Instrument Company, Oregon, USA), following the methodology described by Shackel et al. [44]. Measurements were taken between 1:00 PM and 3:00 PM solar time, selecting young, recently expanded, sun-exposed leaves. At each checkpoint, two plants were evaluated. In treatments T2 and T3, one leaf per plant was measured, yielding a total of six Ψ_{leaf} measurements, the average of which was used for the analyses. In treatment T1, the average was calculated from 12 measurements, taken equivalently at the different CPs.

2.6.3. Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI)

The normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) was derived from Sentinel-2 satellite imagery (Copernicus program, European Space Agency) processed using the Auravant web platform (<https://www.auravant.com>). The NDVI value for each treatment was calculated as the average of all pixel values within the corresponding plot, providing a single representative value for each treatment. This satellite provides images with a spatial resolution of 10 m and a revisit frequency of 3–5 days under favorable atmospheric conditions. For the analysis, only images with cloud cover $\leq 20\%$ were selected. The NDVI was calculated from the near-infrared (B8) and red (B4) spectral bands, through the equation:

$$NDVI = (B8 - B4) / (B8 + B4) \quad (1)$$

This index was used as an indicator of the vegetative state and vigor of the foliar cover.

2.6.4. Yield and quality

For each CP, commercial yield, total yield, and fruit quality were determined. The harvest was carried out on July 24, 2023, and July 25, 2024, when more than 85% of the fruits were red. On each date, 24 plants were harvested within a 9 m² area per sampling point. The fruits were classified into two categories: commercial production, corresponding to red tomatoes of marketable quality, and total production, which included the sum of red, green, and discarded fruits. For quality determination, 30 red fruits were randomly selected at each sampling point, and their total soluble solids content ($^{\circ}\text{Brix}$) was quantified using a digital refractometer (Mettler Toledo, model RE4OD, Columbus, OH, USA).

2.7. Statistical analysis

An ANOVA statistical analysis was performed. When significant differences were detected, a comparison of means was performed by applying Duncan's test at $p < 0.05$. Data were analyzed using the statistical software package IBM SPSS version 24.0 for Windows (IBM Corp. Released 2016. IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 24.0. Armonk, NY, USA).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Meteorological conditions

Table 3 shows the ETo calculated using the Penman–Monteith (ETo-PM) approach, the mean temperature (T_{mean}), the mean relative humidity of the air (RH_{mean}), cumulative rainfall and effective rainfall during the four phenological phases of processing tomato in the two study campaigns (2023 and 2024). The total cumulative ETo-PM was very similar

in both years, with values of 634 mm in 2023 and 618 mm in 2024. In both years, the phase with the highest water demand was rapid vegetative growth (Phase II), followed by the fruit development and ripening phases. These cumulative values fall within the range previously reported for processing tomatoes in Extremadura [11], confirming the crop's high water demand in the region. Regarding temperature, similar average values were observed between campaigns, although in 2023 the rapid vegetative growth and fruit development phases exhibited higher temperatures (19.9 and 26.2 °C) compared to 2024 (18.4 and 22.4 °C). In 2023, higher maximum temperatures were recorded, reaching up to 40.9 °C in Phase III and 39.44 °C in Phase IV, with relatively higher minimums ranging from 4.53 to 14.54 °C. In contrast, during 2024 maximum temperatures were lower in all phases except Phase II, accompanied by lower minimums (3.73–11.21 °C). In both years, during Phase II, there were nine days (out of the 45 that comprise this stage) with maximum temperatures above 32 °C, a value considered a critical threshold associated with floral abortion [45]. The coincidence in both years of several days with maximum temperatures above the critical threshold of 32 °C during Phase II indicates that flowering was subjected to conditions of high physiological risk [45]. These heat episodes can compromise fruit set, reduce the final number of fruits, and thus limit the crop's potential yield, even when water status is adequate. This behavior reinforces the idea that RDI scheduling should consider not only the soil or plant water status but also the occurrence of extreme events, whose intensity and frequency exhibit marked interannual variability even within the same plot. The average relative humidity was higher in 2024 (especially during the transplanting phase, at 66.8%) compared to the lower values in 2023, which resulted in lower evaporative demand. The differences between years were mainly marked by the distribution of precipitation: in 2023, 102.2 mm of total rainfall (53.6 mm effective) were recorded, compared to only 27.1 mm (9.6 mm effective) in 2024.

Table 3. Reference evapotranspiration (ET_o), mean temperature, mean air relative humidity, rainfall and effective rainfall in the three irrigation treatments.

Year	Phases	ET _o -PM (mm)	T _{mean} (°C)	T _{max} (°C)	T _{min} (°C)	RH _{mean} (%)	Rain (mm)	Effective rain (mm)
2023	Phase I	50.57	17.6	29.76	4.53	48.64	5.25	2.07
	Phase II	237.77	19.96	35.35	6.87	55.99	67.27	35.99
	Phase III	186.01	26.15	40.9	14.54	54.64	29.48	15.58
	Phase IV	159.77	25.87	39.44	13.61	45.48	0.2	0
	Total	634.12					102.2	53.64
2024	Phase I	43.36	18.51	29.71	3.86	66.82	0	0
	Phase II	237.77	18.35	37.55	3.73	57.48	8.48	2.85
	Phase III	166.65	22.38	37.79	11.21	58.9	18.58	6.8
	Phase IV	170.09	26.49	30.77	10.94	46.63	0	0
	Total	617.87					27.06	9.65

ET_o-PM is the reference evapotranspiration calculated through the Perman-Monteith equation. T_{mean} is the mean temperature, T_{max} is the maximum temperature, and T_{min} is the minimum temperature. RH_{mean} is the mean relative humidity. Phase I, Phase II, Phase III and Phase IV indicate the different phases of processing tomato.

3.2. Applied water

Figure 6 shows the evolution of the amount of water applied during the processing tomato growing cycle for the 2023 (Figure 6a) and 2024 (Figure 6b) campaigns, in the three

irrigation treatments. In both years, a clear differentiation was observed in the total amount of water applied according to the irrigation strategy employed. In 2023, treatment T1, scheduled based on lysimeter-measured ET_c, recorded a cumulative volume of 586.03 mm, while T2 and T3, managed via the IrriDesK DT, applied 400.58 mm and 304.33 mm, respectively, remaining within the established threshold (<500 mm). In 2024, the values were similar, with T1 receiving 555.14 mm and T2 and T3 293.31 mm and 277.08 mm, respectively. Thus, the IrriDesK treatments managed to keep water application within the established consumption limit, in contrast to T1, which exceeded it in both years (purple dashed horizontal line in Figure 6). Furthermore, the reduction in applied water with the RDI strategies was considerable compared to treatment T1 (~30–45 % depending on year and treatment). However, differences in effective precipitation, maximum temperature, and evaporative demand across growing seasons conditioned the actual severity of stress for the same programmed deficit level. This highlights the complexity of establishing static or generalizable RDI strategies, and the need for decision-support tools—such as DTs—capable of dynamically readjusting water supply based on the crop’s physiological response and evolving climatic conditions.

During the transplantation phase (Phase I), water supply was reduced in all treatments, with a progressive and similar increase across them, corresponding to the crop establishment stage. During this period, the soil is typically near saturation due to pre-sowing irrigation, which allows water inputs to be minimized without affecting the initial establishment of the crop. This initial condition prevents excessive applications at a time when the evapotranspiration demand and the tomato’s water needs are still low [43]. During the rapid vegetation growth phase (Phase II), differences in the applied water volumes were observed among the treatments. In 2023, treatments T1 and T2 received similar volumes (127.55 and 138.68 mm, respectively), while T3 received less water (116 mm). In contrast, in 2024, T1 received a higher volume of water (156.70 mm) compared to T2 (101.61 mm) and T3 (86.04 mm). This phase is characterized by accelerated vegetative growth and high water demand. Adequate water availability during this period is essential to prevent plant stress, as water deficits could induce flower abortion [43]. The results suggest that differences in the amount of water applied could directly influence the physiological condition of the plants and their productive potential. According to Patanè et al. [46], in open field studies, fully replenishing crop evapotranspiration (100% ET_c) during sensitive growth stages such as flowering is a fundamental requirement to achieve maximum processing tomato yield in semi-arid regions. In line with this, Kuşçu et al. [47], in a study conducted under subhumid climatic conditions, reported that the highest marketable yield was obtained with full irrigation, whereas water deficit during one or more sensitive crop stages (especially flowering and fruit set) caused a significant reduction in yield.

During the fruit development phase (Phase III), treatment T1 received a higher cumulative water volume in 2024 (395 mm) compared to 2023 (387 mm). Conversely, treatments T2 and T3 recorded higher irrigation volumes in 2023 (272 mm and 243 mm, respectively) than in 2024 (249 mm and 225 mm, respectively) during the same phase. Previous studies on processing tomatoes have indicated that water scarcity during this critical stage can limit fruit growth and significantly reduce yield [27,43].

During the ripening phase (Phase IV), treatment T1 received a higher volume of water in both years compared to the other treatments. During this period, the differences between treatments became more evident, reflecting the implementation of RDI strategies in treatments T2 and T3. Previous studies indicate that mild stress at this stage promotes the concentration of soluble solids (°Brix), improves fruit quality, and does not affect commercial production [30, 43, 48].

a)

Figure 6. Cumulative water applied in the different irrigation treatments: (a) 2023 and (b) 2024. The black arrows indicate the start and end of the different phases of the processing tomato. The purple dotted horizontal line marks the established water consumption limit.

3.3. Crop water status

Figure 7 shows the Ψ_{leaf} evolution in 2023 (Figure 7a) and 2024 (Figure 7b) for all irrigation treatments.

In the 2023 campaign (Figure 7a), treatment T1 (full lysimeter-scheduled) showed a Ψ_{leaf} evolution with marked variability across phenological phases. During Phases II (rapid vegetative growth) and III (fruit development), Ψ_{leaf} values fell below the reference threshold (green dashed line proposed by Campillo et al. 2006), indicating the onset of water stress during these critical stages. In contrast, during Phase IV (ripening), the Ψ_{leaf} values once again approached the reference threshold, indicating a restoration of the plant's water status. The highest value was recorded in mid-summer during Phase III, with an average Ψ_{leaf} of -0.63 MPa, while the minimum values were reached in Phases II and III, with averages of approximately -0.74 and -0.83 MPa, respectively. With respect to treatment T2 (irrigation scheduled by IrriDesk using an RDI strategy during the ripening phase), Ψ_{leaf} values fell below the reference threshold (dashed pink line) in Phase II and in the second half of Phase III. In Phase IV, the plant recovered its water status, bringing Ψ_{leaf} values above the pre-established threshold. The highest value was recorded at the beginning of Phase II of the crop, with an average Ψ_{leaf} of -0.54 MPa, while the lowest value was reached at the end of Phase III, with an average of -0.93 MPa. The evolution of

Ψ_{leaf} in T3 (irrigation scheduled by IrriDesk using RDI strategies during the transplanta- 480
 tion and ripening phases) was very similar to that of T2, except in Phase III, when an 481
 average minimum value of -1.0 MPa was reached in mid-summer. 482

In 2024 (Figure 7b), the differences in plant water status among the various treat- 483
 ments decreased throughout the entire irrigation season, but especially during Phase II. 484
 The Ψ_{leaf} values in treatment T1 remained below the established threshold during Phases 485
 II and III. In Phase IV of the crop, the Ψ_{leaf} values remained above the established thresh- 486
 old. Treatments T2 and T3 saw that Ψ_{leaf} values dropping slightly below the threshold 487
 during Phase II and remaining above the established threshold in Phases III and IV. In 488
 Phase II, treatment T2 saw an average value of -0.55 MPa, notably higher than that of T3 489
 at the start of the phase, indicating a better initial water status in T2. Some researchers 490
 have previously worked with web platforms that enable automated irrigation by combin- 491
 ing water balance algorithms with soil moisture sensor data [41, 49, 50]. More recently, 492
 Millán et al. [51] demonstrated for the first time in a hedgerow olive orchard that such 493
 algorithms respond appropriately to RDI strategies, maintaining the plant’s water status. 494
 In this study, it is the first time that a DT such as IrriDesK has been validated in processing 495
 tomato by directly analyzing Ψ_{leaf} , confirming its potential to precisely manage irrigation 496
 under drought scenarios. 497

a) 498

b) 499

499

500

501

Figure 7. Seasonal patterns of midday leaf water potential (Ψ_{leaf}) during the 2023 (a) and 2024 (b) seasons in representative plants for each irrigation treatment. In treatment T1, the value shown is the average of twelve measurements \pm standard error. In T2 and T3 treatment, it is the average of six measurements \pm standard error. The green horizontal dotted line indicates the established threshold for Ψ_{leaf} for each phase of processing tomato cultivation irrigated according to the crop's water requirements (100% ETc). The pink horizontal dotted line indicates the established Ψ_{leaf} threshold for each phase of processing tomato cultivation using deficit irrigation strategies. The black vertical dotted lines indicate the beginning and end of each phase. Different letters in the same column indicate statistically significant differences according to Duncan's multiple range test ($p < 0.05$). Letters are not shown when no differences were found.

3.4. Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) dynamics in different irrigation treatments

Figure 8 shows the temporal evolution of the NDVI in the three irrigation treatments during the 2023 (Figure 8a) and 2024 (Figure 8b) campaigns. The NDVI is commonly used as an indicator of vegetative vigor, canopy cover, and, indirectly, the physiological status of crops [52]. In the case of processing tomatoes, it has been reported that values between 0.70 and 0.85 correspond to an adequate physiological state, free from water limitations, especially during the phases of greatest vegetative development [53]. However, an increase in canopy development does not necessarily imply higher productivity. In fact, Pettorelli et al. [54] showed that temporary irrigation interruptions, even when the leaf area index (LAI) partially recovers, can result in commercial yield reductions of up to 33%. These findings highlight that vegetative biomass production does not always translate into a proportional increase in fruit yield, underscoring the importance of complementing physiological indicators with the direct evaluation of productive parameters.

In 2023 (Figure 8a), treatments T1 and T2 exhibited a similar growth pattern throughout almost the entire crop cycle, except for the final phase, during which treatment T2 showed reduced vegetative vigor compared to T1. For its part, treatment T3 began to show a decrease in growth from the second half of Phase II, maintaining NDVI values lower than the other treatments until the end of the cycle. The higher reduction in NDVI observed in T3, and to a lesser extent in T2, during the second half of Phase II and especially in Phase III, coincides with a drop in Ψ_{leaf} towards values near the stress threshold defined for the crop (Figure 7). This behavior confirms that the decrease in vegetative vigor is clearly associated with the water deficit imposed during this sensitive phase, as previously described for processing tomatoes under semi-arid conditions [21]. Consequently, the RDI strategy applied in T3 induced moderate-to-severe water stress during the rapid

fruit growth stage, limiting canopy expansion and explaining the lower NDVI values recorded until the end of the cycle.

In 2024 (Figure 8b), a different behavior was observed: during Phases I and II, all three treatments exhibited a very similar growth pattern. However, from Phase II onwards, a differentiation between the treatments began to emerge, with T1 exhibiting higher NDVI values than the others, reflecting greater vegetative vigor. This separation in vegetative vigor coincides with a lower cumulative water supply in T2 and T3 during Phase II (Figure 6b), which resulted in Ψ_{leaf} values closer to the crop's water stress threshold (Figure 7b). Although this stress was moderate compared to 2023, it appears to have been sufficient to partially limit canopy expansion. Consequently, the NDVI difference observed from this stage onwards can be attributed to the direct effect of water deficit on vegetative growth.

Figure 8. Variation in the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) in the three irrigation treatments: (a) 2023 and (b) 2024. The black arrows indicate the different phases of processing tomato.

3.5. Production and quality

Figure 9 shows total production, commercial production, and total soluble solids content ($^{\circ}$ Brix) for the different irrigation treatments. In both years of the study, significant differences in marketable and total yield were observed among the irrigation treatments. In 2023 (Figure 9a), treatment T1 achieved the highest commercial yield (135.51 t/ha), followed by T2 (96.82 t/ha) and T3 (83.41 t/ha). In 2024, T1 maintained the highest yield (135.54 t/ha), while T2 and T3 produced 90.13 and 108.29 t/ha, respectively, exceeding the regional average of recent years (80,000–85,000 kg/ha). These results confirm that the deficit irrigation treatments (T2 and T3) enabled significant water savings, albeit at the cost of a proportional reduction in commercial yield, especially when the deficit was applied both in the initial phase and during ripening (T3), which is consistent with previous studies on the effect of water stress during critical stages of tomato development [46, 47].

Regarding fruit quality (Figure 9b), an inverse trend to yield was observed: T2 and T3 exhibited higher soluble solids content ($^{\circ}$ Brix) than T1. This is consistent with the findings reported by Giuliani et al. [48] and Campillo et al. [26], who highlight that a moderate water deficit during the ripening phase promotes sugar accumulation and improves the quality of processing tomatoes.

In the current context of climate change, characterized by more frequent and intense droughts, irrigation strategies take on special significance. These extreme conditions reduce the availability of water for crops, increasing the need for efficient resource management. According to Pérez et al. [12], during drought periods, the Extremadura Agrarian Law (Law 6/2015) gives irrigation priority to woody crops over annual crops, such as processing tomatoes. Tools such as the IrriDesK DT enable the optimization of water use and the maintenance of crop viability, even on small plots, thereby increasing profitability per unit of water applied. With a maximum allocation of 5,000 m³/ha, it would only be possible to efficiently sustain plots managed with controlled deficit irrigation (T2 and T3). Thus, the choice of the most appropriate treatment will depend on whether the priority is to maximize total yield (T1) or to balance productivity, quality, and water use efficiency (T2 and T3), demonstrating that smart irrigation management can be key in the face of increasing water stress scenarios.

a)

b)

556

557

558

559

560

561

562

563

564

565

566

567

568

569

570

571

572

573

574

575

576

577

578

579

580

581

582

583

584

585

586

587

588

589

Figure 9. (a) Commercial yield and total yield recorded during the two years of the study for the three irrigation treatments. The dotted red line indicates the separation between the 2023 and 2024 growing seasons, facilitating comparisons between years. The columns represent the means for each type of production, accompanied by error bars indicating the standard error of the mean. (b) Average total soluble solids content (°Brix) in the different irrigation treatments in 2023 and 2024. The different letters above the columns within the same year indicate statistically significant differences according to Duncan's multiple range test ($p < 0.05$), while the absence of letters indicates that no significant differences were found.

4. Conclusions

This study validated, over two consecutive campaigns (2023 and 2024), the use of a digital twin (IrriDesK) for automated irrigation management in processing tomatoes, compared to manual scheduling based on a lysimeter.

- The use of the IrriDesK digital twin proved to be an effective tool for irrigation management in processing tomatoes, validated over two consecutive growing seasons. The system significantly reduced water consumption ($\approx 40\%$) compared to full irrigation, while remaining within the proposed sustainability threshold ($\leq 5,000 \text{ m}^3/\text{ha}$).

- Physiological monitoring (Ψ_{leaf}) confirmed the digital twin's ability to dynamically adjust irrigation strategies, ensuring adequate water status during critical phases, while NDVI analysis showed that greater vegetative vigor does not always translate into higher yield, highlighting the need to combine physiological and productive indicators in decision-making.

- In terms of productivity, full irrigation ensured maximum yield, while deficit irrigation treatments reduced production but improved fruit quality (°Brix), which can represent an economic advantage in water-restricted contexts. Likewise, it was confirmed that applying water deficit in the early stages severely compromises production, whereas in the later stages it can improve quality without affecting commercial yield.

- In summary, the results indicate that integrating digital twins with weather forecasts will enable anticipation of drought and heatwave scenarios, thereby optimizing crop sustainability and resilience.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, S.M., J.M.V. and C.C.; methodology, S.M. and C.C.; software, J.C.; validation, S.M., J.C. and C.C.; formal analysis, S.M.; investigation, S.M.; resources, C.C.;

data curation, S.M. and J.M.V.; writing—original draft preparation, S.M.; writing—review and editing, S.M. and J.M.V.; visualization, S.M.; supervision, C.C. and J.C.; project administration, C.C.; funding acquisition, C.C. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This work was developed in the ET4DROUGHT Project (PID2021-127345OR-C33) funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation in the framework of the State Program for Scientific, Technical and Innovation Research 2021–2023 and the DigiSPAC project (TED2021-131237B-C22).

Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Acknowledgments: I would like to express my gratitude to Eugenio Márquez for his outstanding work in coordinating and executing the agronomic part of the trial.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

RDI	Regulated Deficit Irrigation
Ψ_{leaf}	Leaf Water Potential
ET _c	Crop Evapotranspiration
ET _o	Reference Evapotranspiration
DT	Digital Twin
CPs	Control Points
AI	Artificial Intelligence
IoT	Internet of Things
DSS	Decision Support System
EC _a	Apparent Electrical Conductivity
ET _o -PM	ET _o calculated using the Penman–Monteith
T _{mean}	Mean Temperature
Rh _{mean}	Mean Relative Humidity of the Air
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index

References

- Schmidhuber, J.; Tubiello, F.N. Global food security under climate change. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **2007**, *104*, 19703–19708.
- Vermeulen, S.; Cools, J.; Staes, J.; Van Passel, S. A review of economic assessments of drought risk reduction approaches in agriculture. *Journal of Environmental Management*, **2023**, *345*, 118909.
- An, I. P. C. C. Special report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5 C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change. *Sustainable Development, and Efforts to Eradicate Poverty*, **2018**, *32*.
- Sahani, J.; Kumar, P.; Debele, S.; Spyrou, C.; Loupis, M.; Aragão, L.; Porcú, F.; Shah, M.A.R.; Di Sabatino, S. Hydro-meteorological risk assessment methods and management by nature-based solutions. *Science of the Total Environment*, **2019**, *696*, 133936.
- Şen, Z. *Applied drought modeling, prediction, and mitigation*. Amsterdam: Elsevier, **2015**.

6. Zaidman, M.D.; Rees, H.G. and Young, A.R. Spatio-temporal development of streamflow droughts in north-west Europe. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 6: 2002, 733–751. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-6-733-2002>. 652
7. Porter, J. R.; and Semenov, M. A. Crop responses to climatic variation. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 2005, 360(1463), 2021-2035. 654
8. Kimura, S.; Antón, J.; LeThi, C. Farm level analysis of risk and risk management strategies and policies: cross country analysis, 2010. 656
9. Gutiérrez-Cabanillas, J. I.; Ordiales Rey, E.; Carvajal, M.; Espinosa Borreguero, F. Can the Carbon Dioxide Fixation of Processing Tomato Plants Compensate for the Emissions of the Tomato Industry?. *Agriculture*, 2024, 14(8), 1267. 658
10. World Processing Tomato Council (WPTC).2024. Available online: <https://www.wptc.to/> 660
11. Valcárcel, M.; Lahoz, I.; Campillo, C.; Martí, R.; Leiva-Brondo, M.; Roselló, S.; Cebolla-Cornejo, J. Controlled Deficit Irrigation as a Water-Saving Strategy for Processing Tomato. *Sci. Hortic.* 2020, 261, 108972. 661
12. Pérez, F.L. Ley 6/2015, de 24 de marzo, Agraria de Extremadura. *Actual. Jurídica Ambient.* 2015, 2015, 28–30. 663
13. MAPA. Avance de Superficies y Producciones de Cultivo 2022. In 2022 Anuario de Estadística; Ministerio de Agricultura, Pesca y Alimentación: Madrid, Spain, (In Spanish). Available online: <https://www.mapa.gob.es/es/estadistica/temas/publicaciones/anuario-de-estadistica/2023/default.aspx?parte=3&capitulo=07&grupo=6&seccion=27> (accessed on 21 August 2025). 664
14. Girona, J., Mata, M., Goldhamer, D. A., Johnson, R. S., & DeJong, T. M. (1993). Patterns of soil and tree water status and leaf functioning during regulated deficit irrigation scheduling in peach. *Journal of the American Society for Horticultural Science*, 1993, 118(5), 580-586. 668
15. Amayreh, J.; Al-Abed, N. Developing crop coefficients for field-grown tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) under drip irrigation with black plastic mulch. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2005, 73, 247–254 671
16. Fusheng, M.; Shaozhong, K.; Mixia, W. Research advance and prospect of regulated deficit irrigation on fruit trees. *Agricultural Research in the Arid Areas* 2005, 23(4), 225-228. 673
17. Egea, G.; Nortes, P.A.; González-Real, M.M.; Baille, A.; Domingo, R. Agronomic response and water productivity of almond trees under contrasted deficit irrigation regimes. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2010, 97, 171–181. 675
18. Ju, Y. L.; Xu, G. Q.; Yue, X. F.; Zhao, X. F.; Tu, T. Y.; Zhang, J. X.; Fang, Y. L. Effects of regulated deficit irrigation on amino acid profiles and their derived volatile compounds in Cabernet Sauvignon (*Vitis vinifera* L.) grapes and wines. *Molecules*, 2018, 23(8), 1983. 677
19. Memmi, H.; Gijón, M.C.; Couceiro, J.F.; Pérez-López, D. Water stress thresholds for regulated deficit irrigation in pistachio trees: Rootstock influence and effects on yield quality. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2016, 164, 58–72. 680
20. Moñino, M.J.; Blanco-Cipollone, F.; Vivas, A.; Bodelón, O.G.; Prieto, M.H. Evaluation of different deficit irrigation strategies in the late-maturing Japanese plum cultivar ‘Angeleno’. *Agric. Water Manag.* 2020, 234, 106111 682
21. Campillo, C. Estudio para el diseño de un sistema de recomendación de manejo de agua en rotaciones de cultivo hortícolas en las Vegas del Guadiana. 2007. 684
22. Pruitt, W. O.; Angus, D. E. Large weighing lysimeter for measuring evapotranspiration.1960. 686
23. Young, M. H.; Wierenga, P. J.; Mancino, C. F. Large weighing lysimeters for water use and deep percolation studies. *Soil Science*, 1996, 161(8), 491-501. 687
24. Allen, R.G.; Pereira, L.S.; Raes, D.; Smith, M. *Crop Evapotranspiration: Guidelines for Computing Crop Water Requirements*. Irrigation and Drainage, 56; FAO: Rome, Italy, 1998. 689
25. Mancha, L. A.; Uriarte, D.; Prieto, M. D. H. Characterization of the transpiration of a vineyard under different irrigation strategies using sap flow sensors. *Water*, 2021, 13(20), 2867. 691
26. Campillo, C.; Márquez, E.; Muñoz, P.; Dorado, T.; Sánchez-Porro, A.; González, V. Effects of regulated deficit irrigation on total soluble solids evolution in processing tomato. In XVI International Symposium on Processing Tomato, 2022, 1351 (pp. 13-18). 693
27. Ripoll, J.; Urban, L.; Brunel, B.; Bertin, N. Water deficit effects on tomato quality depend on fruit developmental stage and genotype. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 2016, 190, 26-35. 696
28. Lu, J.; Shao, G.; Cui, J., Wang, X., Keabetswe, L. Yield, fruit quality and water use efficiency of tomato for processing under regulated deficit irrigation: A meta-analysis. *Agricultural Water Management*, 2019, 222, 301-312. 698
29. Quadir, M.; Hickey, M.; Boulton, A.; Hoogers, R. Effect of deficit irrigation on TSS in tomatoes. *National Vegetable Industry Centre*, 2006, 36-37. 700

30. Johnstone, P. R.; Hartz, T. K.; LeStrange, M.; Nunez, J. J.; Miyao, E. M. Managing fruit soluble solids with late-season deficit irrigation in drip-irrigated processing tomato production. *HortScience*, 2005, 40(6), 1857–1861. 702
703
31. Millán, S.; Montesinos, C.; Casadesús, J.; Vadillo, J. M.; Campillo, C. Use of a Digital Twin for Water Efficient Management in a Processing Tomato Commercial Farm. *Agronomy*, 2025, 15(9), 2132. 704
705
32. Alves, R.G.; Maia, R.F.; Lima, F. Development of a Digital Twin for smart farming: Irrigation management system for water saving. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2023, 388, 135920. 706
707
33. Guo, Z.; Hu, S.; Jin, W.; Ye, Y.; Shan, C. Application of Digital Twin in the Industry of Axial Hollow-Wall Pipes. *Applied Sciences*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13148093> 708
709
34. Katzin, D.; Marcelis, L.F.; van Henten, E.J.; van Mourik, S. Heating greenhouses by light: A novel concept for intensive greenhouse production. *Biosyst. Eng.* 2023, 230, 242–276. 710
711
35. Wang, L. Digital twins in agriculture: A review of recent progress and open issues. *Electronics*, 2024, 13, 2209. 712
36. Martelli, A.; Rapinesi, D.; Verdi, L.; Donati, I.I.M.; Dalla Marta, A.; Altobelli, F. Smart irrigation for management of processing tomato: A machine learning approach. *Irrig. Sci.* 2024, 1–18. 713
714
37. Galaverni, M.; Oddi, G.; Preite, L.; Belli, L.; Davoli, L.; Marchioni, R.; Solari, F.; Beghé, D.; Ganino, T.; Vignali, G.; Ferrari, G. An IoT-based data analysis system: A case study on tomato cultivation under different irrigation regimes. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 2025, 229, 109660. 715
716
717
38. Moral, F.J.; Terrón, J.; Da Silva, J.M. Delineation of management zones using mobile measurements of soil apparent electrical conductivity and multivariate geostatistical techniques. *Soil Tillage Res.* 2010, 106, 335–343. 718
719
39. Bouyoucos, G.J. Directions for Making Mechanical Analyses of Soils by the Hydrometer Method. *Soil Sci.* 1936, 42, 225–230. 720
721
40. Picón-Toro, J.; González-Dugo, V.; Uriarte, D.; Mancha, L.A.; Testi, L. Effects of canopy size and water stress over the crop coefficient of a “Tempranillo” vineyard in south-western Spain. *Irrig. Sci.* 2012, 30, 419–432. 722
723
41. Casadesus, J.; Mata, M.; Marsal, J.; Girona, J. A general algorithm for automated scheduling of drip irrigation in tree crops. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 2012, 83, 11–20. 724
725
42. Bellvert, J.; Pelechá, A.; Pàmies-Sans, M.; Virgili, J.; Torres, M.; Casadesús, J. Assimilation of sentinel-2 biophysical variables into a digital twin for the automated irrigation scheduling of a vineyard. *Water*, 2023, 15, 2506 726
727
43. Campillo, C.; González, J.Á.; Fortes, R.; Millán, S.; González, V.; Chávez, Á.; Daza, C.; Prieto, M.H. Manual Práctico de Riego del Tomate de Industria. Grupo de Riego y Nutrición del Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura (CICYTEX). 2015. Available online: <https://cicytex.juntaex.es/documents/46972/95615/Manual+pr%C3%A1ctico+de+riego+de+tomate+de+industria/0b2c625a-8eca-4e7d-84ef-8dc80d5568e9> 728
729
730
731
44. Shackel, K.A.; Ahmadi, H.; Biasi, W.; Buchner, R.; Goldhamer, D.; Gurusinghe, S.; Hasey, J.; Kester, D.; Krueger, B.; Lam-pinen, B.; et al. Plant Water Status as an Index of Irrigation Need in Deciduous Fruit Trees. *Hort Technol.* 1997, 7, 23–29. 732
733
45. Jones Jr, J. B. *Tomato plant culture: in the field, greenhouse, and home garden.* CRC press. 2007. 734
46. Patanè, C.; Tringali, S.; Sortino, O. Effects of deficit irrigation on biomass, yield, water productivity and fruit quality of processing tomato under semi-arid Mediterranean climate conditions. *Sci. Hortic.*, 2011, 129:590–6. 735
736
47. Kuşçu, H.; Turhan, A.; Demir, A. O. The response of processing tomato to deficit irrigation at various phenological stages in a sub-humid environment. *Agricultural Water Management*, 2014, 133, 92–103. 737
738
48. Giuliani, M. M.; Gatta, G.; Nardella, E., Tarantino, E. Water saving strategies assessment on processing tomato cultivated in Mediterranean region. *Italian Journal of Agronomy*, 2016, 11(1), 738. 739
740
49. Bacci, L.; Battista, P.; Rapi, B. An integrated method for irrigation scheduling of potted plants. *Sci. Hortic.* 2008, 116, 89–97. 741
50. Osroosh, Y.; Peters, R.T.; Campbell, C.S.; Zhang, Q. Comparison of irrigation automation algorithms for drip-irrigated apple trees. *Comput. Electron. Agric.*, 2016, 128, 87–99. 742
743
51. Millán, S., Campillo, C., Casadesús, J., Pérez-Rodríguez, J. M., & Prieto, M. H. Automatic irrigation scheduling on a hedge-row olive orchard using an algorithm of water balance readjusted with soil moisture sensors. *Sensors*, 2020, 20(9), 2526. 744
745
52. Gomez, J.A.; Zarco-Tejada, P.J.; García-Morillo, J.; Gama, J.; Soriano, M.A. Determining Biophysical Parameters for Olive Trees Using CASI-Airborne and Quickbird-Satellite Imagery. *Agron. J.* 2011, 103, 644–654. 746
747
53. Mastrorilli, M.; Campi, P.; Palumbo, A.D.; Modugno, F. Ground-based remote sensing for assessing tomato water-status. *Ital. J. Agron.* 2010, 5, 177–183 748
749
54. Pettorelli, N.; Vik, J.O.; Mysterud, A.; Gaillard, J.M.; Tucker, C.J.; Stenseth, N.C. Using the satellite-derived NDVI to assess ecological responses to environmental change. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* 2005, 20, 503–510. 750
751

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.

752
753
754